

Synthesis of some New Bis-azoles and -azines

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Recently, we have described the synthesis of benzoxazine and quinazolinone derivatives¹ 4-Quinazolones generally exhibit interesting biological activities² This led us to synthesise some new quinazolone and benzoxazine systems

The diacid chloride (1) is a versatile reagent for the synthesis of bis-heterocyclic systems Thus, aminolysis of 1 using aniline gave the amide (2) Reaction of 1 with bifunctional reagents was investigated Thus, keeping compound 1 and *o*-phenylenediamine at room temperature gave the acylated product (3) Cyclisation of 3 using acetic anhydride yielded the benzimidazole derivative (4) Reaction of 1 with *o*-aminophenol yielded the amide (5) Treatment of 1 with anthranilic acid gave the amide (6) Refluxing of 6 with acetic anhydride resulted benzoxazine (7) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Benzoxazine (7) with its reactive center is a versatile reagent for further functionalisation and ring transformation Thus, treatment of 7 with aniline yielded the diamide (8) instead of the expected quinazolinone (9) Fusion of 7 with hydrazine gave *N*-aminoquinazolinone (10) Condensation of the latter with benzaldehyde afforded Schiff base 11 Fusion of 7 with formamide resulted in ring transformation, affording the quinazolinone (12) Refluxing of ethanolic solution of 7 and acetylacetone in the presence of ethoxide produced ring opening, affording benzoylated acetylacetone (13) IR spectra of 13 revealed a broad band at 3230–3150 cm⁻¹, characteristic of the intramolecular hydrogen bond

Experimental

All mps are uncorrected IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a Varian VN (S 60 T) instrument All compounds gave satisfactory microanalytical results for C, H and N

Formation of 2 A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and aniline (0.02 mol) in glacial acetic acid was left at room temperature for 0.5 h The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as colourless crystals (68%), m.p. 175°, ν_{max} 3250 (NH), 1690 cm⁻¹ (C=O)

Formation of 3 A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and *o*-phenylenediamine (0.02 mol) in glacial acetic acid was left at room temperature for 0.5 h The resulting solid was crystallised from acetic acid as pink crystals (71%), m.p. 211°, ν_{max} 3200–2400 (NH-NH₂) 1600 cm⁻¹ (CO)

Cyclisation of 3 Compound 3 (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 1 h in acetic anhydride (10 ml), then left to cool and poured in water The resulting solid was crys-

tallised from acetic acid to afford buff crystals of **4** (65%), m.p. 145°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 400 (NH), 1 650 cm^{-1} (CO).

Formation of 5 : A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and *o*-aminophenol (0.02 mol) in glacial acetic acid was left at room temperature for 0.5 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from methanol as buff crystals (55%), m.p. 86°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 100–3 600 (NH-OH), 1 730 cm^{-1} (CO); δ 4.7 (4H, s, 2OCH₂), 6.3–8.3 (2H, m, ArH), 9.1 (2H, s, 2 × NH), 9.6 (2H, s, 2 × OH).

Formation of 6 : A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and anthranilic acid (0.02 mol) in glacial acetic acid was left at room temperature for 1 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as pale yellow crystals (67%), m.p. 263°; $\nu_{\max}$ 2 900–3 150 (NH-OH), 1 740 cm^{-1} (CO).

Formation of benzoxazine (7) : Compound **6** (0.01 mol) was refluxed in acetic anhydride (10 ml) for 1 h, then concentrated and left to cool to yield colourless solid (42%), m.p. 161°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 725 (CO), 1 640 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Formation of 8 : A mixture of **7** (0.01 mol) and aniline (0.02 mol) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as colourless crystals (63%), m.p. 247°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 670–3 200 (NH-OH), 1 690 cm^{-1} (CO); δ 4.7 (4H, s, 2 × OCH₂), 6.8–8.7 (22H, m, ArH), 9.9 (2H, s, 2 × NH), 12.2 (2H, s, 2 × NH).

Formation of 10 : A mixture of **7** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine (0.02 mol) was fused at 120° in an oil-bath for 3 h. The product obtained was crystallised from ethanol as colourless crystals (59%), m.p. 101°; $\nu_{\max}$

3 600–3 250 (NH), 1 700 (CO), 1 630 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Formation of Schiff's base 11 : A mixture of **10** (0.01 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.02 mol) was fused at 100° in an oil-bath for 3 h. The product obtained was crystallised from acetone as brown crystals (32%), m.p. 158°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 690 (CO), 1 610 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Formation of 12 : A mixture of benzoxazinone (**7**; 0.01 mol) and formamide (0.02 mol) was heated at 170° in an oil-bath for 2 h. The product obtained was crystallised from acetic acid as colourless crystals (59%), m.p. 224°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 600–2 830 (NH), 1 720 (CO), 1 620 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ 4.6 (4H, s, 2 × OCH₂), 6.7–8.7 (12H, m, ArH), 11.7 (2H, s, 2 × OH).

Formation of 13 : A mixture of **7** (0.01 mol), acetylacetone (0.02 mol) and sodium ethoxide (0.03 mol) in absolute ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The reaction mixture was poured in ice-cold dilute HCl to give solid product which was crystallised from acetic acid as colourless crystals (48%), m.p. 186°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 230–3 150 (OH), 3 000 (NH), 1 740 (CO), 1 610 cm^{-1} (C=N).

References

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